

eDNAqua-Plan

NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Workflows and data storage approaches currently used in European aquatic DNA-based biodiversity monitoring

Deliverable 2.3

Work Package 2

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Executive Summary

This report contains an inventory of the workflows used in aquatic eDNA-based biodiversity monitoring in Europe. The inventory is based on manual research of guidelines and standards, manual search of reports from commissioned eDNA-based biomonitoring, the questionnaire survey developed within this work package, and automated collection of metadata from BioSamples in INSCD databases.

The conclusions highlight the need for standardized workflows and metadata requirements to support the scalability of eDNA monitoring in Europe and to ensure data adheres to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

Metadata and Data Storage: Current practices for storing European eDNA-related data in databases like BioSamples, GBIF, and OBIS were reviewed. Data from commissioned eDNA biomonitoring is seldom stored in publicly accessible databases. Written reports from smaller consultancy companies are often not public, and if they are, they lack bibliographic indexes. Compilation of metadata from European samples stored in the public databases showed that metadata is often incomplete, particularly in terms of sampling protocols and DNA extraction methods. Geographic data is often not in a standardized format. The lack of standardized metadata hampers data reusability.

The report identifies several critical gaps, including:

- Limited accessibility to national protocols published only in local languages.
- Inconsistent submission of eDNA data to repositories, leading to difficulties in finding and using this information.
- The need for harmonized standards to ensure comparability across datasets from different regions and institutions.

Recommendations:

The document stresses the importance of promoting open access to national monitoring protocols and international cooperation on standard development. It suggests exploring whether submission of eDNA data to repositories can be mandated, and highlights a need for incentives for proper documentation and metadata compliance.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
³ BIOPOLIS	Associação Biopolis
DDBJ	DNA Data Bank of Japan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
⁹ EBI	European Bioinformatics Institute
EC	European Commission
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EU	European Union
⁷ EV ILVO	Eigen Vermogen Van Het Instituut Voor Landbouw - En Visserijonderzoek
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GSC	Genomic Standards Consortium
⁸ IHU	Diethens Panepistimio Ellados
INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
LifeWatch-ERIC	E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
MixS	Minimum Information about any(x) sequence
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
² NIVA	Norsk institutt for vannforskning / Norwegian Institute for Water Research
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
SRA	Sequence Read Archive
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
SU	Sorbonne Université
¹ SYKE	Suomen ympäristökeskus / Finnish Environment Institute
⁵ UDE	Universitaet Duisburg-Essen
⁴ ULOD	Uniwersytet Lodzki
UMINHO	Universidade do Minho
⁶ UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
UVEG	Universitat de Valencia
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut Voor de Zee
WP	Work Package(s)
WU	Wageningen University

Dictionary of terms used in this report

Term	Definition
BioProject (in INSDC)	A collection of biological data related to a single initiative, originating from a single organization or from a consortium.
BioSample (in INSDC)	The BioSample database contains descriptions of biological source materials used in experimental assays. One or more sequencing runs can be associated with the same BioSample.
Commissioned eDNA biomonitoring	eDNA surveys paid for either by government institutions (such as environmental agencies) or private companies, performed by either commercial eDNA companies or research institutes
Darwin Core	A standard for sharing information about biological diversity
Environment Ontology (ENVO)	ENVO is a domain ontology concerned with "environments" of all kinds and aims to promote standardisation and interoperability of diverse data sets through the concise, controlled description of environment types
MixS checklist	A MixS checklist contains minimal information about a type of nucleotide sequence. There are several checklists designed for various types of organisms, and extension checklists for capturing metadata about the environment from which the sequence originates.

Identified gaps

Table 1: Gaps identified in workflows and data storage approaches currently used in European aquatic eDNA-based biodiversity monitoring.

“Participant type”	Gap	Consequence	Suggested solutions
National monitoring agency	Internal protocols and guidelines not published or not findable; many published in national language only	A comprehensive review of workflows and guidelines is difficult	Encourage open access publishing of guidelines and protocols, with the most critical information given also in English
Scientific and practitioner community	Lack of method standards	Plurality of methods, risk of incomparable data and problems in harmonising European-level data sets	International standard development
Contractee or researcher	Metabarcoding data from commissioned eDNA biomonitoring are seldom submitted to repositories	Data not Findable or Accessible	Develop incentives for commissioners and contractees to submit data Make sequence and metadata submission easier by having a submission system that is as easy as possible, but also by providing clear guidelines/a FAQ section
	Occurrences based on eDNA seldom registered in biodiversity repositories	Data not Findable	Same as for metabarcoding data
Data repository infrastructure	BioSample metadata until now seldom contains information on sampling protocol, size fraction, DNA isolation protocol. Geographic coordinates not on standardised format	Difficult to query databases, reusability is limited	Draw more attention to the MIxS ID fields e.g., samp_collect_device, size_frac, nucl_acid_ext (https://www.genesc.org/pages/standards/all-terms.html)

	The definitions of types of data records in the INSDC databases is unclear (e.g., a BioSample vs. a Sequencing run or Nucleotide record).	Difficult for researchers to know which metadata to submit at which step → inconsistent metadata	Provide a clearer explanation of the different types of data records and the required metadata based on the nature of the data in the INSDC databases.
Data standards	Low granularity in the Darwin core DNA-derived data metadata related to bioinformatic processing	Difficult to enter sufficient metadata about the bioinformatic processing → limits interoperability	DwC DNAderived data is a work in progress
	Need for harmonisation between various metadata checklists	Limited interoperability	This will be addressed in WP3 in eDNAqua-Plan

1. Introduction

Recent years have seen an exponential increase in aquatic eDNA data generated by numerous laboratories across Europe. Along with academic research, an increasing number of eDNA surveys are conducted by consulting companies, commissioned by either governmental institutions or private companies. Concurrently with this increase, there is an increasing number of efforts towards developing regional and national guidelines (see e.g. Bruce et al., 2021; Pawlowski et al. 2021) and international standards for eDNA-based biomonitoring of aquatic environments. These efforts focus on various parts of the workflow, or the entire workflow, including sampling, laboratory work and bioinformatic processing. Dedicated international standards working groups in CEN 230 WG 28 and ISO/TC 147/SC 5/WG13 "Environmental DNA and RNA methods" has been established and efforts to engage the international eDNA community in standardisation has been actively made through the International eDNA Standardisation Task Force iESTF (www.iestf.global). Some prominent examples of national eDNA roadmaps for the implementation of these new methods into environmental monitoring exist (e.g. Norros et al. 2022; De Brauwer et al. 2023; Kelly et al. 2023; The National Aquatic eDNA Strategy 2024).

Most scientific journals currently have strict data accessibility requirements, meaning that eDNA sequence data presented therein needs to be submitted to one of the major sequence repositories (overview in D2.2). Despite data accessibility requirements in scientific journals, reviews of scientific literature have shown that researchers often do not make proper use of the data availability section (Shea et al. 2023, Hassenrück et al. 2021). Furthermore, to our knowledge, few efforts have been conducted to obtain an overview of the data dissemination and storage practices in either commercial eDNA monitoring, eDNA monitoring commissioned by national or local authorities, or molecular monitoring performed within transnational directives such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). Proper documentation of such commissioned eDNA biomonitoring is crucial for stakeholders - both the commissioners and the society which is affected by any decisions made based on eDNA data. As the market for eDNA monitoring is quickly growing, incentivizing data sharing according to FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) is of interest to the greater scientific and biomonitoring community.

To assess the state of workflow documentation and identify gaps in eDNA-based monitoring across Europe, T2.3 in WP2 aimed to inventory the existing workflows, starting from sampling methodologies through bioinformatic pipelines, and, by extension, evaluate how these workflows are documented. To achieve this, we first needed to identify each step in an eDNA-based biomonitoring workflow. It follows that each such of these steps could then be described in a corresponding metadata field associated with the data. Several consortia and working groups focus on developing metadata checklists, e.g., the Minimal Information about any(X) Sequence (MlxS) from the Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC) (Yilmaz et al. 2011). In WP3 of the eDNAqua-Plan project, an alignment model for community eDNA metadata standards will be developed and used as a foundation to propose recommendations for improving traceability. In T2.3, we draw on the work already done in WP3, to I) identify metadata fields which can be used in a manual revision of commissioned eDNA biomonitoring and II) identify which metadata fields included in existing checklists (such as MlxS) should be leveraged for extracting information on the tools and parameters used in eDNA research workflows in Europe across eDNA repositories.

Metadata associated with an aquatic eDNA sample can broadly be categorized as follows:

- **geographical** (latitude, longitude, depth in water column, environment type)
- **sampling** (date-time of sampling, water collection device, volume, filter)
- **isolation of eDNA** (sample preservation and isolation protocol)

In The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) the entity "BioSample" may be used to store the information up to and including isolation of eDNA. Note that more than one type of sequencing can be obtained from the same eDNA sample, thus additional information needs to be associated with a "sequencing run", such as the sequencing strategy (e.g. shotgun or amplicon). If amplicon sequencing (metabarcoding) is performed, relevant metadata are e.g., the targeted genetic marker, the primer pair used, the description of the PCR protocol and the type of sequencing platform. Raw data outputs from the sequencing platform, which have only been subjected to minimal bioinformatic processing, are usually deposited in primary sequence repositories. The most common are the INSDC databases, such as the Sequence Read Archive (SRA). In contrast to the sequences deposited in the nucleotide databases (e.g.,

NCBI-nt), the single reads within a file submitted to SRA are not given a taxonomic assignment. Over the past decades, platforms and repositories for submitting raw sequence data (mainly the INSDC databases) have been developed. Submitted data are assigned accession numbers which can be used to identify the data in research papers and reports. These repositories may be referred to as primary repositories.

It is generally accepted that sequence data obtained from high-throughput sequencing needs extensive cleaning, filtering and de-noising to obtain meaningful sequence variants which correspond to a biological taxonomic level (e.g., family, genus or species, depending on the taxonomic resolution of the marker region). Such bioinformatic workflows, often referred to as pipelines, consist of several steps and usually involve one or more of the following: quality check, trimming of sequences based on quality scores (each nucleotide in a sequence read has an associated score indicating how reliable it is), merging paired-end reads, removing “noise” introduced during PCR and sequencing by various algorithms, and grouping very similar sequences into either amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) or Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs). Finally, chimeric sequence variants (i.e., artifact SVs which are a result of the merging of two pieces of real sequences from different taxa) are often removed. The choice of a bioinformatic pipeline, in particular the algorithm for taxonomic assignment, may influence the result of metabarcoding-based species inventories (Mathon et al. 2021, Hleap et al. 2021).

The submission of ASVs or OTUs to biodiversity portals is less established, but the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) are developing procedures for this. When submitting processed sequence data, often with associated taxonomic annotation of each sequence variant, the bioinformatic workflow and reference taxonomic database with a timestamp should also be documented. In this context, a metabarcoding sequence variant with the corresponding taxonomic assignment from a given sample may be viewed as an “occurrence”. Thus, the Darwin Core standards are increasingly used to organise the metadata associated with sequence variants submitted to biodiversity portals. (See e.g., Abarenkov et al. (2023)). An overview of the properties of various primary and secondary eDNA repositories is presented in Deliverable D2.2.

To summarise - the path from an environmental sample to a biodiversity inventory based on processed sequencing data with taxonomic annotation contains numerous steps and choices, each of which may influence the results. To be able to develop useful standards and recommendations, it is necessary to have an overview of how the workflows are documented. Furthermore, it is important to assess the extent to which submitters submit metadata and submit it correctly, so-called ‘metadata compliance’, *sensu* Hassenrück et al. (2021). It is of utmost importance to the scientific community and stakeholders that future biodiversity data obtained through eDNA are as well-documented as possible, and adhere to the FAIR principles, i.e., Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

2. Methods

The investigation of current DNA-based biodiversity monitoring workflows used in Europe was conducted using four approaches to cover complementary and sometimes overlapping parts of the eDNA-based biomonitoring:

1. Literature review of guidelines and standards.
2. Manual search for reports presenting results from commissioned eDNA-based biodiversity monitoring in aquatic environments.
3. Results from the WP2 questionnaire survey.
4. Search in primary and secondary eDNA repositories for records representing aquatic environmental DNA collected in Europe (NCBI+ENA BioSamples, OBIS, GBIF), and analysis of the corresponding metadata.

A. Literature review of guidelines and standards

1. Guidelines

Relevant guidelines were compiled by the members of the consortium (Table 3). These were assessed for methodological scope, taxonomic scope, which sample type they were relevant for (i.e., water, sediment or both), if they used qPCR/dPCR or metabarcoding or both, and if they included recommendations regarding bioinformatic processing and publication of data.

2. Standards

Websites www.iso.org and <https://www.cencenelec.eu/> were visited in August 2024, and the search terms environmental DNA, eDNA, PCR, and amplicon were entered. The search results were manually checked to ensure that the found standards actually were relevant for eDNA-based biomonitoring. Further, the

information gathered by International eDNA Standardization Task Force iESTF <https://iestf.global/> working groups was used to complement the list of available standards.

B. Manual search for commissioned eDNA biomonitoring

Based on Google searches, knowledge in the consortium and information from the website [eDNA Labs — eDNA RESOURCES](#) (last access 15.09.2024), we compiled a list of European research institutes and companies appearing to be involved in eDNA biomonitoring (Table S1). The websites of these companies or institutes were manually searched for aquatic eDNA biomonitoring reports. For each report, we compiled a set of metadata, described in Table S2. We focused in particular on the ecological scope and methodology for identification of taxa, i.e., whether qPCR or metabarcoding was used, the targeted marker region, bioinformatics pipeline and reference database. Furthermore, we registered whether the sequence data and/or observations were submitted to a repository, and whether the report document itself had a digital identifier.

C. Automated collection of BioSamples metadata

The [BioSample databases](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/) (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/>) stores submitter-supplied descriptive information, or metadata, about the biological materials from which data stored in the INSDCs primary data archives are derived (Courtot et al. 2019). The BioSample database can be searched with various search terms, and the search can be limited to BioSamples with associated SRA (Sequence Read Archive) data. All of the sequence linked biosamples metadata are in the INSDC databases NCBI, ENA and DDBJ. An example of a BioSample is shown in Figure 1 (below). The submitter-supplied information is typically stored in the “Attributes” field. The categories/fields within the attributes may be GSC defined terms (e.g., “sample material processing”) or may be defined by the user (e.g., “temperature”). Various checklists exist for submitting BioSample metadata, and the mandatory terms vary between checklists. In addition the user can add “attribute” fields as they see fit..

MIMARKS Survey related sample from freshwater metagenome

Identifiers	BioSample: SAMN03839980; Sample name: EV51; SRA: SRS1192268	
Organism	freshwater metagenome unclassified entries; unclassified sequences; metagenomes; ecological metagenomes	
Package	MIMARKS: survey_water: version 6.0	
Attributes	collection date	2013-01
	depth	0-20 cm
	broad-scale environmental context	Deciduous woodland
	local-scale environmental context	Pond
	environmental medium	water
	geographic location	France
	latitude and longitude	48.6897 N 1.9164 E
	ammonium	0.23 mg/l
	chlorophyll	13.93 ug/l
	conductivity	252 uS/cm
	dissolved organic carbon	18.4 mg/l
	dissolved oxygen	65.3 %
	nitrate	6.35 mg/l
	nitrite	0.089 mg/l
	pH	6.92
	phosphate	0.04 mg/l
	sample material processing	Water prefiltered on 5um, sample collected on 0.2 um filter
	sample size	400 ml
	temperature	7 C
Description	Water sample from Etang des Vallees (pond) Keywords: GSC.MixS,MIMARKS.6.0	
BioProject	PRJNA305428 freshwater metagenome Retrieve all samples from this project	

Figure 1. Example of metadata associated with a BioSample submitted to NCBI.

The search of the BioSample database had the following aims: 1) assess the extent to which sampling protocol and eDNA-isolation protocol are included in the metadata, 2) get an overview of the most used methods in European research (to the extent possible), 3) obtain an overview over the type of metadata which are submitted in the BioSample attributes.

We used the NCBI interface to search the BioSample database. To identify samples representing environmental DNA, we considered multiple search terms. In addition to “environmental DNA” or “eDNA”, an aquatic metagenome can be considered to comprise all the DNA found in an aquatic environment. We therefore also searched for “metagenome” within “water”, “wastewater” and “sediment”, and selected only samples which also had associated SRA records. During the search, we realized that BioSamples which are first created in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) were not retrieved if any of the “Environmental packages” were checked. (The database a BioSample was originally submitted to can be identified by the 4th letter in the BioSample accession number, according to <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/docs/faq>). We therefore also searched for “metagenome” and “ERC000024”, which is the code for the GSC MixS water checklist. The exact search terms are shown in Table 7 under “Results”. Some samples had values in attribute fields associated with genome assembly (“assembly.software”, “assembly.quality”). Manual inspection showed that these samples represented either metagenome assemblies of genomes of single bacterial species, or assembled genomes from organisms grown in water samples. At least the latter may be considered outside the definition of environmental DNA, therefore we removed records with values in these fields.

A list of the BioSample accession numbers of each search result was downloaded, and the corresponding metadata (specifically *attributes*) were retrieved with the script *biosample2table.py*, obtained from [stajichlab/biosample_metadata: Extract metadata from biosamples in NCBI \(github.com\)](https://github.com/stajichlab/biosample_metadata). The script was

modified to include a try-except which let the process continue in case the search for an accession number returned an error (e.g. “404 page not found”). The script returns a .tsv-table where the (list of) column names is the union of all attribute names/fields found in the list of BioSamples, and the rows contain the attribute information from the BioSamples. The information in the table was processed in R v. 4.3.2 (R Core Team, 2023). The R scripts can be found in the GitHub repository [eDNAAqua-Plan-project/wp2: The code and data contributing to the activities of WP2 \(github.com\)](https://github.com/eDNAAqua-Plan-project/wp2).

We compiled the names of the attribute fields from all the BioSample records retrieved by the searches. The fields defined by GCS which we consider related to sampling and DNA-isolation are listed in Table 2 (MIXS v5 information, copied from <https://www.gencs.org/pages/standards/all-terms.html>, accessed 05.09.2024.), and the MIXS extension water ([Extension: water \(Water\) - mixs \(genomicsstandardsconsortium.github.io\)](https://github.com/genomicsstandardsconsortium/mixs), accessed september 2024).

Table 2. List of MIXS fields leveraged for extracting information on eDNA research workflows from BioSample metadata.

MIXS ID	Label	Structured comment name	Definition
MIXS:0000002	sample collection device or method	samp_collect_device	The method or device employed for collecting the sample
MIXS:0000016	sample material processing	samp_mat_process	Any processing applied to the sample during or after retrieving the sample from the environment. This field accepts OBI, for a browser of OBI (v 2018-02-12) terms please see http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/OBI
MIXS:0000017	size fraction selected	size_frac	Filtering pore size used in sample preparation
MIXS:0000735		size_frac_low	Mesh/pore size used to pre-filter the sample
MIXS:0000736		size_frac_up	Mesh/pore size used to retain the sample
MIXS:0000001	amount or size of sample collected	samp_size	Amount or size of sample (volume, mass or area) that was collected
MIXS:0000111		samp_vol_we_dna_ext	Volume (ml) or mass (g) of total collected sample processed for DNA extraction
MIXS:0000037	nucleic acid extraction	nucl_acid_ext	A link to a literature reference, electronic resource or a standard operating procedure (SOP), that describes the material separation to recover the nucleic acid fraction from a sample

Samples from European waters were selected by looking for names of European countries (exact match) in any metadata field containing the string “geo”, e.g., geo_loc_name, or when possible, filtering by latitude and longitude (not including overseas territories), according to [Extreme points of Europe - Wikipedia](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Extreme_points_of_Europe). The resulting locations were manually screened to ensure that they were on European territory.

We also assessed the extent to which the codes proposed by the Environment Ontology project (Buttigieg et al. 2013) were used to identify the environment the sample was taken from. The number of records which used these codes was found by counting the number of records which contained the string “ENVO” (case-insensitive) in the fields “env_medium”, “env_local_scale” and “env_broad_scale”.

D. Manual search for metadata in secondary eDNA repositories

The active secondary eDNA repositories identified in T2.2 were the biodiversity portals OBIS and GBIF. OBIS was searched for DNADerived datasets via the web interface (<https://obis.org/datasets>, last accessed 24.09.2024). Here “DNADerivedData” was selected in the “Dataset type” drop-down menu. Occurrence records within the DNA-derived datasets were obtained via the OBIS mapper ([OBIS Mapper](https://obis.org/mapper)), by creating a

“layer” with the extension DNADerivedData. Gbif was searched for DNA derived occurrences by using “All filters” and selecting the following options in the drop-down menus: Continent: Europe, “Sample size unit”: “DNA sequence reads”, “Occurrence status”: “Present”. With this search c. 2M records were retrieved. We then selected “DNA derived data” in DWCA extension, this reduced the number of records to c. 234,660.

3. Results

A. Literature review of guidelines and standards

1. Guidelines

Relevant guidelines were compiled by the members of the consortium (Table 3). These were assessed for methodological scope, taxonomic scope, which sample type they were relevant for (i.e., water, sediment or both), if they used qPCR/dPCR or metabarcoding or both, and if they included recommendations regarding bioinformatic processing and publication of data.

Table 3. List of visited guidelines, roadmaps, strategies and reviews

Authors	Year	Title	Link
Abarenkov et al.	2023	Publishing DNA-derived data through biodiversity data platforms	https://docs.gbif.org/publishing-dna-derived-data/en/
Abbott et al.	2021	Guidance on the use of targeted environmental DNA (eDNA) analysis for the management of aquatic invasive species and species at risk. Department of Fisheries and Oceans Canada	https://waves-vagues.dfo-mpo.gc.ca/library-bibliotheque/40960791.pdf
Bruce et al.	2021	A practical guide to DNA-based methods for biodiversity assessment	https://repository.oceanbestpractices.org/bitstream/handle/11329/2094/AB_article_68634_en_1.pdf?sequence=1
De Brauwer et al.	2023	Best practice guidelines for environmental DNA biomonitoring in Australia and New Zealand	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdfdirect/10.1002/edn3.395
De Brauwer et al.	2022	Environmental DNA test validation guidelines.	https://research.csiro.au/environomics/wp-content/uploads/sites/187/2022/08/Environmental-DNA-test-validation-guidelines.pdf
De Brauwer et al.	2022	Environmental DNA protocol development guide for biomonitoring.	https://research.csiro.au/environomics/wp-content/uploads/sites/187/2022/08/Environmental-DNA-protocol-development-guide-for-biomonitoring.pdf
eDNA TASK TEAM	2024	US National Aquatic eDNA Strategy	https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/NSTC_National-Aquatic-eDNA-Strategy.pdf
Hakimzadeh et al.	2024	A pile of pipelines: An overview of the bioinformatics software for metabarcoding data analyses	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/1755-0998.13847
Kelly et al.	2023	Toward a national eDNA strategy for the United States.	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdfdirect/10.1002/edn3.432
Loeza-Quintana et al.	2020	Pathway to Increase Standards and Competency of eDNA Surveys (PISCeS)—Advancing collaboration and standardization efforts in the field of eDNA	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/edn3.112

Makiola et al.	2020	Key questions for next-generation biomonitoring	https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/environmental-science/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2019.00197/full
Minamoto et al.	2020	An illustrated manual for environmental DNA research: Water sampling guidelines and experimental protocols	https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.121
Melchior and Baker	2023	eDNA Guidelines and field protocols for lotic systems	https://niwa.co.nz/sites/default/files/2024-05/eDNA%20guidelines%20report_12122023%20FINAL%20%283%29.pdf
Norros et al.	2022	Roadmap for implementing environmental DNA (eDNA) and other molecular monitoring methods in Finland–Vision and action plan for 2022–2025	https://helda.helsinki.fi/server/api/core/bitstreams/5564049d-1f93-4468-80f5-0cd079940782/content
Pawlowski et al.	2020	Environmental DNA applications in biomonitoring and bioassessment of aquatic ecosystems	https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/en/home/topics/water/water--publications/publications-water/environmental-dna-applications-in-biomonitoring-and-bioassessment.html
Takahashi et al.	2023	Aquatic environmental DNA: A review of the macro-organismal biomonitoring revolution	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0048969723009385
Zaiko et al.	2022	Towards reproducible metabarcoding data: Lessons from an international cross-laboratory experiment	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/1755-0998.13485

2. Standards

The standards which we considered related to DNA workflows are listed in Table 4. In all, we selected 13 standards. Altogether, the standards covered several of the steps in the workflow, but some were limited in the taxonomical scope. It should be noted that since all the standard documents are behind a paywall (the price to obtain a permanent pdf-copy ranged from c. 20-250 EUR), the scope of each standard is inferred from the title and brief abstract.

- **Sampling:** Two standards, one for environmental DNA in general, and one specifically for benthic diatoms
- **Reference barcodes:** Management of reference barcodes from benthic diatoms
- **Barcoding for identification of foodstuffs:** two standards were developed for barcoding of fish and bivalves to ensure food authenticity. Although the sample material is not environmental DNA, we consider these standards relevant for applications of eDNA methods in fisheries and aquaculture.
- **DNA isolation and library preparation for sequencing:** one standard with a general taxonomic scope
- **Bioinformatic processing:** one general standard and one specifically for shotgun metagenomic sequences. The latter also covers archiving and metadata
- **Data formatting and archiving:** One general standard for life sciences
- **qPCR/dPCR and microarray:** While these techniques do not generate sequence data, they are frequently used to detect species based on eDNA. We found one standard which was specifically developed for detection of *Legionella* by qPCR, and two standards describing the application of qPCR/dPCR and microarray in general.

Table 4. List of the ISO and CEN standards and technical reports related to DNA molecular methods.

Title	Topic	Workflow step	Taxonomic scope	Standard code
Water quality - Sampling, capture and preservation of environmental DNA from water	Water quality	Sampling	general	CEN 17805:2023
Water quality - Technical report for the routine sampling of benthic diatoms from rivers and lakes adapted for metabarcoding analyses	Water quality	Sampling	benthic diatoms	CEN/TR 17245:2018
Technical report for the management of diatom barcodes	Water quality	Reference barcodes	benthic diatoms	CEN/TR 17244:2018
Foodstuffs. DNA barcoding of fish and fish products using defined mitochondrial cytochrome b and cytochrome c oxidase I gene segments	Food	Barcoding	fish	CEN/TS 17303:2019
Food authenticity. DNA barcoding of bivalves and products derived from bivalves using a defined mitochondrial 16S rRNA gene segment	Food	Barcoding	bivalves	22/30455163 DC BS EN 17881
Massively parallel sequencing — Part 1: Nucleic acid and library preparation	Biotechnology	DNA isolation, library preparation	general	ISO 20397-1:2022
Massively parallel sequencing — Part 2: Quality evaluation of sequencing data	Biotechnology	Bioinformatic processing	general	ISO 20397-2:2021
Massively parallel DNA sequencing - General requirements for data processing of shotgun metagenomic sequences	Biotechnology	Data processing, archiving and metadata	general	ISO/TS 24420
Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences	Biotechnology	Data formatting	general	ISO 20691:2022
Biobanking. General requirements for biobanking	Biotechnology	Biobanking	general	ISO 20387:2020
Biotechnology. Requirements for evaluating the performance of quantification methods for nucleic acid target sequences. qPCR and dPCR	biotechnology	qPCR, dPCR	general	ISO 20395:2019
Water quality — Detection and quantification of Legionella spp. and/or Legionella pneumophila by concentration and genic amplification by quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR)	water quality	qPCR	Legionella	ISO/TS 12869-2:2024
Molecular biomarker analysis — Requirements for microarray detection of specific nucleic acid sequences	Biotechnology	Microarray	general	ISO 16578:2022

In addition to the standards already published, there are many ongoing efforts to develop more targeted standards. The International eDNA Standardization Task Force (iESTF) coordinates resources and knowledge from the eDNA community to promote the adoption of international standards. iESTF collaborates with researchers, policymakers, industry stakeholders, and ISO working groups to establish minimum quality requirements and support the development of adaptable, high-quality procedures for various applications. iESTF working groups are currently writing draft documents which will be given to ISO TC 147 WG 13 during the upcoming meeting in South Korea, October 28th 2024. More information on iESTF working groups can be found in Table 5.

Table 5. iESTF working groups

iESTF working group	Leader(s)
ISO EN 17805:2023 Sampling, capture and preservation of environmental DNA from water	Kristian Meissner (FIN)
Preservation and extraction of macroinvertebrate bulk samples	Florian Leese (DE)
Sampling, preservation and extraction of benthic periphytic diatoms	Martyn Kelly (UK) John Darling (USA)
Measuring quality and quantity of extracted DNA	Cathryn Abbott (CAN)
Target species detection	Katy Klymus (USA)
Metabarcoding to survey biological communities	Donald Baird, Mehrdad Hajibabaei (CAN), Kirsty Deiner (CH)

B. WP2 questionnaire

1. Results from the WP2 questionnaire survey - submission of metadata

See also Deliverable 2.2.

Table 6. Self-reported submission of metadata, obtained from the WP2 questionnaire survey.

Type of eDNA sequence repository	Metadata field	Percent of respondents indicating that they include it
Primary (raw sequence data)	Sampling method	59%
	DNA extraction	51%
	PCR protocol	2% (1 out of 60)
	Sequencing protocol or platform	56%
Secondary (processed sequence variants with taxonomic annotation)	Sampling method	51%
	DNA extraction	51%
	PCR protocol	0%
	Sequencing protocol or platform	46%

C. Manual search for commissioned eDNA biomonitoring in Europe

1. Geographical coverage and trend over time

In all, we examined 79 reports. However, for 34 of these, the full text was not available, and we inferred some information from the title. The majority of the investigated studies took place in Norway or Sweden, with 29 and 32 studies, respectively. Finland, Denmark and Belgium were represented with 8, 7 and 3 studies, respectively. The majority of studies with full text available were commissioned by government agencies. The commissioner of the report could not be inferred from the reports where the full text was not available. The reports were dated from 2017-2024, and there was an increase in the number of reports per year, from 4 in 2017-2019 to 21 in 2022.

There was a bias in the collection of reports, as 50% were produced by MIX Research, Sweden (private consulting company) and 25% by Norwegian Institute for Nature research (NINA). Others were various private or public research institutes and a few private consulting companies.

Figure 2. A) Number of reports submitted per year and distribution by country. B) Distribution of type of commissioner of the reports.

2. Data submission and dissemination

Reports from research institutes were in all cases archived with an unambiguous identifier such as uri or doi. By contrast, reports from commercial companies usually did not have any identifiers. In the 45 reports accessible to download, none of them specified whether the data (sequences or qPCR results) had been made public in a repository.

3. Ecological scope and methodology

A range of biodiversity questions and issues were addressed in the reports which we investigated. Generally, the studies fell within one or more of five categories, listed in decreasing order: “community inventories”, “detection of endangered species”, “detection of invasive species”, “detection of pathogens” and “detection of pathogens and their host” (Figure 3A). For 49 reports, methodology of species detection could be found in the full text or inferred from the title. Of these, half had used single-taxa assays in the investigation (qPCR, ddPCR or dPCR), 14 (30%) had used metabarcoding, 5 had used both qPCR and metabarcoding. Three reports described only eDNA sampling, not the subsequent molecular analyses (Figure 3B). In several cases more than one question was addressed in the same report, e.g., inventory of a local fish community by metabarcoding and detection of invasive species by qPCR. (Therefore, the total number in Figure 3A is higher than the number of reports.) In one case, eDNA was used to trace a natural resource (kelp) in sediment.

Figure 3. A) Distribution of ecological questions addressed by the investigations in the reports. B) Methods used for detection and inventorying of taxa.

Information on the marker genes used was given in all the reports, but the marker region or information on the primers such as the primer sequence or reference were not always given. The most commonly used metabarcoding marker genes were 12s for fish, COI and ITS (Figure 4A). In the reports where the full text was publicly available, bioinformatic pipelines were in most cases not described or otherwise documented. The name of the reference database used for taxonomic assignment of metabarcoding data was usually provided. NCBI-nt was the most used, in some cases together with internal, unpublished databases (Figure 4B).

Figure 4. A) Distribution of marker genes used for metabarcoding. B) Reference database used for taxonomic assignment of metabarcoding data

D. Workflow insights from BioSamples “attributes”

1. Submission portal influences the metadata

BioSample data are shared across the INSDCs. However, from an initial screening of our data it appears that the type of metadata and the names of metadata fields are influenced by which database the data were first submitted to. Although a detailed analysis is beyond the scope of this task, the BioSamples which were initially submitted to ENA (accession numbers starting with SAME) had often e.g., separate fields for latitude and longitude, whereas BioSamples submitted to NCBI (accession numbers starting with SAMN) had the two coordinates in the same field.

2. European representation

Searching for the terms “environmental DNA” or “eDNA”, associated with either the “water” environmental package or the ERC000024 checklist in NCBI retrieved in total c. 8500 BioSample records (Table 7). Replacing “eDNA” with “metagenome” in these searches retrieved in total c. 118,000 records. Identifying all the BioSamples of European origin proved challenging, due to some lack of standardization of the name of the metadata field where geographic coordinates were entered, and also because the geographic coordinates were given according to different systems or formats. We therefore identified European BioSamples according to the “geo_loc_name” field (see “Methods” section above). This identification is not exact, but the estimated number of BioSamples of European origin are c. 2200 and 32700, respectively.

Table 7: Overview over search terms used to obtain accession numbers of BioSamples associated with aquatic environmental DNA, and information about the data retrieved with each search term.

Search #	Search term	Total number of hits	Estimated number of BioSamples from Europe (%)	Number of attribute fields, European samples
A	"environmental DNA"[All Fields] AND "water"[filter] AND "biosample sra"[filter]	1793	1 (0.08%)	10
B	"environmental DNA"[All Fields] AND ERC000024[All Fields] AND "biosample sra"[filter]	226	189 (85%) (From two institutions)	
C	"eDNA"[All Fields] AND "water"[filter] AND "biosample sra"[filter]	3764	86 (2.7%)	35
D	"eDNA"[All Fields] AND ERC000024[All Fields] AND "biosample sra"[filter]	2758	1930 (71%)	43
E	"metagenome"[All Fields] AND ("water"[filter] AND "biosample sra"[filter])	92311 (subsample: 10000)	17% based on subsampled data	~300
F	"metagenome"[All Fields] AND ERC000024[All Fields] AND "biosample sra"[filter]	26966	17053 (63%)	~350
G	"metagenome"[All Fields] AND ("wastewater"[filter] AND "biosample sra"[filter])	22393 (subsample:10000)	46% based on subsampled data	

3. Use of ENVO's biome classes in European BioSamples

The use of the Environmental Ontology biome classes to describe the environment.

Table 8. The percentage of European BioSamples who *do* use the Environmental Ontology biome classes in each of the fields 'env_medium', 'env_local_scale' or 'local.environmental.context' and 'env_broad_scale', for datasets retrieved with search B+D, E, F and G.

Search terms	env_medium	env_local_scale	env_broad_scale
B+D ("eDNA" or "environmental DNA" +"ERC000024")	9%	12%	12%
E ("metagenome"+ "water" pkg)	34%	33%	35%
F ("metagenome"+"ERC000024")	30%	23%	30%
G ("metagenome"+ "wastewater" pkg)	62%	62%	60%

4. Insights into eDNA workflows from BioSamples attribute data

In general, there was limited information about the sampling workflow in the BioSample attributes. Among the samples obtained with the search for "metagenome water sra" or "metagenome ERC000024 sra" <6% of the BioSamples included information on the sample collection, processing, size fraction and DNA extraction protocol.

Table 9. Percentage of European BioSamples which have included various MIxS-defined terms related to sample collection and processing in the metadata (BioSample attributes).

GSC/MIxS defined term	Percent of samples with information	Examples of information entered
samp_collect_device	5-6%	"9 cm ice corer", "CTD rosette, Niskin bottle", "Sterivex (0.22 µM)"
size_frac	4-6%	"0.2 micro-meter", "free living", "large particle associated"
samp_mat_process	5-6%	Filter pore size, DNA extraction kit, storage conditions, description of sampling process
samp_vol_we_dna_ext	4%	Numeric values, however the unit associated with the numbers could not be found
nucl_acid_ext, DNA_extraction_method or nucleic.acid.extraction	<1% for NCBI, 6% for ENA	Name of kit, doi of publication with protocol

E. Search of workflow-related metadata entered in secondary eDNA repositories

The OBIS data set search listed 46 datasets with the DNADerivedData extension. Manual inspection showed that one of these was from Europe (United Kingdom). This dataset comprised 1,068,660 sequence records, distributed among 751,140 occurrence records, in all representing 86 species. It was not straightforward to select only occurrences based on aquatic samples in Gbif. Examples of occurrence records on .json-format (the DNA part) from OBIS and Gbif are shown in Figure 5 A and B, respectively. The DwC DNADerived data extension includes fields for workflow metadata such as sample volume, molecular lab protocols, sequencing methods, OTU clustering, reference database for taxonomic annotation and annotation algorithm. However, there is as of yet no field specifically designated to the sequence denoising method.

A

```
"dna": [
  {
    "level": 0,
    "DNA_sequence": "GTAGGTGAACCTGCGGAAGGATCATTAGTGAATATTAGCGCATCTCTTCGGAGAGCGTGACCTCCACT",
    "env_broad_scale": "None",
    "env_local_scale": "None",
    "env_medium": "None",
    "lib_layout": "Paired end, only used forward only",
    "nucl_acid_amp": "Christmas et al., 2023",
    "nucl_acid_ext": "Christmas et al., 2023",
    "otu_class_appr": "Sequences agglomerated at taxonomic rank: Genus",
    "otu_db": "NCBI nr database (accessed 10/11/2020)",
    "otu_seq_comp_appr": "blastn 2.6.0+ e-value cutoff: 0.001",
    "pcr_primer_forward": "CTTGTCATTTAGAGGAAGTAA",
    "pcr_primer_name_forward": "ITS1F",
    "pcr_primer_name_reverse": "ITS2",
    "pcr_primer_reference": "https://earthmicrobiome.org/protocols-and-standards/its/",
    "pcr_primer_reverse": "GCTGCGTCTTCATCGATGC",
    "samp_vol_we_dna_ext": "1L",
    "seq_meth": "Illumina HiSeq 2500",
    "sop": "https://earthmicrobiome.org/protocols-and-standards/its/",
    "target_gene": "ITS",
    "target_subfragment": "ITS1"
  }
]
```

B

```
publishingCountry "ZZ"
protocol "DWC_ARCHIVE"
lastCrawled "2024-09-12T00:30:20.741+00:00"
lastParsed "2024-09-12T02:43:04.774+00:00"
crawlid 364
extensions
  http://rs.gbif.org/terms/1.0/DNADerivedData 2 items
    0
      http://rs.gbif.org/terms/dna_sequence "TG CAG AAT CCC GTGA ACC ATCG AG TTT TGA ACC GCA AG TTG CG CCC GA AG CT TTT AG -CTG AG GG CAC GTC
      GAG GG GA AG GAG GA -TG GT CT C -C -CG TGG -CT C ACC G -GC -CG CG GT GGC CTA AAA ATCG GAG CC CTC G -GC AT CG -GG AT GTC GCG GC GAT AG GT GG --1
      C -GC -TGT GCC -A -AT -G -TG AG CT CGA -AG -GAC -CCT -TT -GA -TGT TGC CT TGT GC -AAC CA AAC CG TTG CG ACC CC CAG GT CAG GC GGG GC TAC CC CG -TC
      ATT CCC CTAG TAA CG GC GAG CGA ACC G -GGA ATAG CCC AG CT TTA AAA TCG GC GCG CT TGC CT TCC GA"
      https://w3id.org/mixs/0000044 "ITS2"
    1
      http://rs.gbif.org/terms/dna_sequence "AAG TGT TGG ATTTAA AG CTG GTTAA AG AT TACA AA TTG ACT TATT AT ACT CCT GAG TATG AA ACC CTAG AT
      ACC CGA AGA AG CAG GG GCTG CAG TAG CCG CCG AGT CT TCTAC GGG TAC ATG GACA ACTGTATG GACC GAC GACTTACC AGTCTTGATCGTTACA AAGG/
      TTG TATGTAG CGTAC CCCTTAGACCTTTT GAG GA AGG CTCTGTTACTA AAC ATGTTTAC GTCCATTGTGGGTAATGTAATTTGGGTTCAAAGCCTTGCGTGCTC
      TAGGCCCCCTCACGGTATCCAAGTTGAAAGAGATAAATTGAACAAGTATGGCCGCTCCCTATTGGGATGCACATTAAACCTAAATGGGGTTATCTGCTA
      TTACCAAAGATGATGAAAACGTGAACTCCCAACCAATTT"
      https://w3id.org/mixs/0000044 "ybcl"
basisOfRecord "MATERIAL_SAMPLE"
occurrenceStatus "PRESENT"
taxonKey 3085897
```

Figure 5. Screenshots showing parts of the .json-files associated with DNA-derived occurrences in A) OBIS and B) GBif.

4. Discussion

A. Current state of aquatic eDNA monitoring in Europe

1. Data dissemination and storage practices in commissioned eDNA biomonitoring

Our results indicate that commissioned aquatic eDNA biomonitoring has been increasing in Europe over the last years. However, there may be regional differences within Europe, as few examples of commissioned eDNA monitoring were found outside of the Nordic countries. Applications include early detection of invasive species and pathogens, tracing endangered species and inventory of local communities of aquatic species. Awareness of eDNA as a relatively practical and low-cost method for biodiversity monitoring seems to exist both among government and private stakeholders. However, obtaining a full overview over the landscape of commissioned eDNA monitoring in Europe is challenging, since there are few, if any, standards or agreed upon best practices for the publication of these data. During our manual search, we noticed that reports from larger research institutes always had a digital object identifier, and were registered in national publishing archives, which makes the reports accessible through e.g. Google Scholar. By contrast, results from smaller consultancy companies often end up as “grey literature”, i.e., materials and research published outside the traditional channels (Schöpfel 2010). In general, such literature often lacks bibliographic indexes, which makes it difficult to access, but the combined value of such literature may be high (Lawrence et al. 2014). Furthermore, national, government-funded reports are often published in native languages, to ensure that biomonitoring funded by taxpayers is accessible to the public. To be accessible through Google Scholar for the international scientific community, it is therefore essential that they contain keywords or a summary in English. Translation tools are becoming increasingly more powerful, and thus language is becoming less of a barrier than it once was. Nevertheless, the sheer volume of research which is being published makes manual search through research papers and reports increasingly time-consuming. To ensure that results from commissioned eDNA monitoring are accessible to the greater scientific community, there is a need to incentivize data dissemination on sequence and biodiversity portals, along with information-rich metadata.

It was beyond the scope of this task to investigate the reasons for lack of data dissemination from this type of eDNA research. However, we may speculate that since commissioned research is often published outside of the scientific journals, the data accessibility requirements are less strict. Thus, neither commissioners or the companies or research institutes have an incentive to consider data dissemination in their budget. Smaller, recently established commercial companies may not have the budget to pay for bibliographic services, and thus do not obtain digital identifiers for their reports. Although there are developed standards which address data archiving of high-throughput sequencing data (e.g., ISO/TS 24420), obtaining a copy of these standards may be prohibitively expensive. Non-disclosure agreements imposed by commissioners may also prevent data sharing.

2. Documentation of workflows in eDNA research

Metadata compliance on the user side when submitting to INSDC

Our investigation shows that users submitting eDNA-based sequence data to INSDC repositories seldom submit metadata about their sampling and laboratory workflows. Furthermore, ENVO is used to describe the environment in less than half of the submissions associated with the water package or checklist. We did not assess whether there is a trend over time in which information the users submit. Submitters who described their samples as “environmental DNA” or “eDNA” seem to be less aware of the ENVO than submitters who use the “wastewater” package. Our results are consistent with the findings of Hassenrück et al. (2021), who investigated metadata from sequencing read runs representing metabarcoding of ecological metagenomes. They found that a minority of sequencing runs were compliant with a MixS checklist and environmental package, that most sequencing runs did not have metadata specifying any of the three Environment description parameters, and that even when provided, ENVO terminology was inconsistently used. Investigating the reasons for why users submit sparse metadata would require more extensive questionnaires or interviews, which is beyond the scope of this task. However, more than half of the participants in our questionnaire survey responded that they include information on sample collection, DNA extraction and sequencing platform in their metadata, which is considerably higher than the percentages of BioSamples with this information. This suggests that the respondents in our survey are more engaged and enthusiastic about this topic than average. As the authors of this document have been on the user side of submitting data to ENA and NCBI, we may speculate in possible reasons for the sparse metadata: the sequencing data are often submitted after a long process of data analysis and manuscript preparation, and the user may just be exhausted and not have the time or energy to delve into what the various checklists mean. Furthermore, since the submission system and checklists are designed to accommodate a wide range of sample types, it may be difficult to identify the most appropriate for one’s own data. Finally, we came

across some minor, but inconvenient issues, such as that for numerical sample collection data such as volume and size fraction it is not clear what the unit is, unless it is entered as text string along with the numbers.

Metadata in biodiversity portals (secondary eDNA repositories)

The results from searching the biodiversity portals OBIS and GBIF revealed that as of yet few eDNA-based species inventories are registered in these portals. Thus, to obtain records of species or taxa based on eDNA, researchers and stakeholders would have to search through scientific journals and reports. The biodiversity portals represent a resource of immense value, and the investment return for society in such portals is estimated to be up to 10-fold (Deloitte report 2023). This value would only increase if eDNA-based biodiversity data were also systematically included. However, to enable future meta-analyses of biodiversity datasets, the metadata needs to be information-rich and correctly formatted. The DarwinCore DNADerived data is an extension to the DarwinCore Occurrence and Event core, designed to capture information related to DNA. This extension is still evolving. Currently, it includes fields related to OTU clustering, but the descriptions may be confusing to the users, as e.g., “otu_class_appr” seems to be associated with a checklist applied to virus genomes ([Term: OTU classification approach \(otu class appr\) - mixs \(genomicsstandardsconsortium.github.io\)](https://github.com/genomicsstandardsconsortium/otu_classification_approach_otu_class_appr_mixs)). Furthermore, we were unable to identify a field specifically suited to describe the “denoising” algorithm of metabarcoding data, such as DADA2. In Europe, e.g., the Genetic tools for Ecosystem health Assessment in the North Sea region (GEANS) project is comparing different bioinformatics pipelines across different laboratories and discussion is ongoing to address workflow-based differences in North Sea species identification. A similar effort is ongoing within the MARCO-BOLO project [MARCO-BOLO Data analysis challenge - Marco-Bolo \(marcobolo-project.eu\)](https://marcobolo-project.eu), where researchers are invited to analyze pre-existing metabarcoding datasets with their “favourite bioinformatic pipeline”. Considering that the bioinformatic pipeline may influence the resulting taxon inventory, we suggest further developing the DwC DNADerived extension to include unambiguous metadata fields capturing bioinformatic pipeline parameters (addressed in WP3).

Workflows in scientific papers

To obtain a full overview over the workflows used in eDNA-based biodiversity studies hitherto published in scientific papers, a large language model, mining scientific literature is a promising tool. While not included in the original project description, such a model has been developed within WP2, and trained on > 100 scientific papers. The training set was compiled to enable the model to identify papers describing eDNA-based studies, and to identify and describe different parts of the workflows, and parameters such as laboratory protocols, marker gene and reference database. Preliminary results from this model are presented in Deliverable 2.2. Optimisation of the model to obtain results suitable for D2.3 was not feasible within the timeframe of WP2, but the work on this model will continue throughout the eDNAqua-Plan-project.

B. Vision and next steps for European DNA-based Biodiversity Monitoring

Open publishing of protocols and method guidelines is essential to facilitate the exchange of best practices, which serves as the groundwork for developing international method standards. It is crucial to follow existing method standards, particularly those related to eDNA, as well as other relevant standards, to ensure shared minimum requirements. Enhancing interaction between academic researchers who are pushing the boundaries of new methodologies and agencies responsible for routine monitoring will help smooth the path for the adoption of new methods and method improvements into international standards. Furthermore, promoting the easy submission of eDNA data to repositories will enable the capture of diffuse data sources, such as local environmental status and impact assessments, and should include data submission in environmental consultant contracts. Additionally, it is important to enhance the submission of data beyond metabarcoding, including qPCR and long-read sequences. Emphasizing the significance of good metadata is vital for being able to retrieve data which can establish references for assessing change and impact, particularly concerning the goals outlined in the Marine Strategy Framework Directive and the Water Framework Directive. We also need to unify and promote the practice of supplying metadata to BioSamples while enhancing the interoperability of various data standards and metadata checklists.

5. Conclusions

The field of aquatic eDNA biomonitoring is inherently very diverse, due to the great variety of environments being surveyed, as well as the taxonomic scope of each survey and the ecology of the targeted species. Thus, standardisation of this field is challenging but necessary to allow comparable large scale assessments of biodiversity patterns based on molecular data in support of European environmental directives. The

development of minimum acceptance criteria for molecular data and associated metadata should be a primary goal moving forward. Development of such minimum criteria should follow co-creative and inclusivity principles and build on already existing schemes. Currently collected metadata in INSDC archives seldom contains information on sampling protocol, size fraction or DNA isolation protocol; these are strongly worth considering. Indeed it would be even better for reusability of data if the associated workflow had been captured systematically. Even metadata frequently collected are often not in standardised formats e.g. geographic coordinates, which would help interoperability.

Once collectively defined, the minimum criteria schemes should enter European or international standardisation pipelines to assure their uptake and long term maintenance. It is important that the future data deposition in line with minimum criteria data is made mandatory for stakeholders dealing with official monitoring schemes in support of European environmental legislation.

In addition to further development of metadata checklists (see T3.3), more focus on making the metadata submission process accessible and easy to understand.

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7. Data/code access

All the data compiled in this task, along with the code used for analyses can be found in [eDNAqua-Plan-project/wp2: The code and data contributing to the activities of WP2 \(github.com\)](https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/wp2).

8. Supplementary

Table S1: List of institutes and companies surveyed in the manual search for aquatic eDNA biomonitoring projects.

Name	Country	Type
MIX Research	Sweden	Consulting company (private)
Norwegian institute for Nature research (NINA)	Norway	Research institute (private)
Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA)	Norway, Denmark	Research institute (private)
DTU Aqua	Denmark	Research institution (academic)
Seanalytics	Sweden	Consulting company (private)
AquaBiota	Sweden	Consulting company (private)
eDNA solutions AB	Sweden	Consulting company (private)
Ramboll	Finland, Sweden, Norway, Denmark, Great Britain	Consulting company
BioName Oy	Finland	Consulting company
Alleco Oy	Finland	Consulting company
Finnish Environment Institute Syke	Finland	Research Institution
Natural Resources Institute Finland	Finland	Research Institution

Table S2: Metadata collected from commissioned eDNA monitoring reports

Part of workflow	Metadata field	Description
Miscellaneous	title	Title of the report
	doi	doi of the report
	year	Publication year
	company_institution	Name of the company or institution who performed the survey
	commissioner	Name of the commissioner of the survey
	commissioner_govt_industry	Whether the commissioner was a government/public agency or private industry.
Sampling	sample_material	The type of material which was collected (e.g., sediment or water)
	samp_collect_device	The device used to collect material
	pore_size	The pore size of the filter used to collect eDNA
	filter_type	The type of filter
	storage	How the sample was stored
Molecular lab work, including sequencing	nucl_acid_ext	Name of the extraction kit or protocol
	metabarcoding_qpcr	Whether the eDNA was analyzed with metabarcoding or qPCR/dPCR/ddPCR or both
	target_gene	Name of target gene, e.g., 18s, COI
	target_subfragment	Name of the subfragment used as marker, e.g., 18s V4
	primer_name_cit	The names or citation for the primers used
	seq_platform	The name of the sequencing platform, e.g., MiSeq, NovaSeq
Bioinformatics	read_processing	The name of the program used to process metabarcoding data (only the program name, no parameter settings)
	ref_db_tax_assign_meta	The name of the reference database which was used for taxonomic assignation of metabarcoding OTUs/ASVs. Either a database or "not_given" or "NA" (not applicable, if metabarcoding was not performed)
	dev_new_primers	Were new primers developed in the study (yes/no)
	ref_db_dev_new_primers	The name of the reference database which was used to design new primers. Either a database or "not_given" or "NA" (not applicable)
Data dissemination	metabar_subm	Whether the metabarcoding data have been submitted to a repository
	qpcr_subm	If qPCR-based observations have been submitted to a biodiversity portal/repository
	metabar_repository	The name of the repository where metabarcoding sequences were submitted (if they were submitted)

	qpcr_obs_repository	Name of the repository where qPCR observations were submitted (if applicable)
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